

LITTLE HOST: Hosting for Animals

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Abstract:

This course completion work aims to develop a website for hosting domestic animals, those that are part of the family and cause concern for their guardians, as it can often happen that certain environments do not allow the presence of their animals, environments such as hotels, farms, beaches, and resorts, especially during tourism and holiday seasons, highlighting the tutor's need to find an alternative. Fortunately, applications and websites created to solve various problems, such as animal care, began to emerge. Therefore, this project seeks to understand the necessary care for pets, to complete the development of a website for hosting pets, specifically for dogs and cats, presenting tutors with qualified hosts who can perform the pet hosting service, trained in the necessary care for different types of animals and, for hosts, employment opportunities.

Resumo:

O presente trabalho tem como objetivo desenvolver um *website* para intermediar o contato entre tutores e anfitriões para a hospedagem de animais domésticos. Estes que muitas vezes são considerados como parte da família, podem ser motivo de preocupação de seus tutores quando, em algumas situações de lazer e viagem, determinados ambientes como, por exemplo, hotéis, sítios, praias e resorts, entre outros locais turísticos, não permitem a presença de animais no recinto. Neste contexto, evidencia-se a necessidade do tutor encontrar uma alternativa que acolha o animal. Felizmente, existem aplicativos e *websites* criados com fins de solucionar diversos problemas sociais, entre eles estão os serviços de cuidados animais. A partir desta circunstância, este projeto busca compreender os cuidados necessários com animais de estimação a fim de concluir o desenvolvimento de um *website* que ofereça serviços de hospedagem para animais domésticos, especificamente, para cães e gatos. O *website* apresentará aos tutores, anfitriões capacitados a realizar os cuidados pertinentes aos diferentes tipos de animais e os anfitriões cadastrados, por sua vez, terão novas oportunidades de emprego.

Resumen:

El presente trabajo tiene como objetivo desarrollar un sitio web para mediar el contacto entre tutores y anfitriones para el alojamiento de animales domésticos. Estos, que suelen ser considerados parte de la familia, pueden ser motivo de preocupación para sus tutores cuando, en algunas situaciones de ocio y viajes, ciertos entornos comerciales como hoteles, granjas, playas y resorts, entre otros lugares turísticos, no permiten la presencia de animales en el recinto. En este contexto, se evidencia la necesidad de que el tutor encuentre una alternativa que acoja al animal. Afortunadamente, existen aplicaciones y sitios web creados con el propósito de resolver diversos problemas sociales, entre ellos se encuentran los servicios de cuidado de animales. A partir de esta circunstancia, este proyecto busca comprender los cuidados necesarios de las mascotas para poder completar el desarrollo de un sitio web que ofrezca servicios de alojamiento para animales domésticos, específicamente, para perros y gatos. La página web presentará a los tutores anfitriones capacitados para llevar a cabo el cuidado pertinente de diferentes tipos de animales y los anfitriones registrados, a su vez, tendrán nuevas oportunidades laborales.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past, the animals, today named domestic animals, were seen as contingent. According to Thomas (2010), in the centuries XVII and XVIII the presence of animals, in the family environment was dispensable, and domestication it was seen by men as synonymous with sovereignty and social subordination.

However, over the centuries, humans began to see animals as creatures that need care and attention, and currently, animals, which were previously seen as despicable creatures, are now seen as part of the family, becoming animals. domestic. Broom and Frazer (2010) state that interactions between domestic animals and humans can develop relationships of friendship and companionship.

The animals have become a concern, they no longer serve merely as an object of exploitation and have become creatures that people seek to care for, feed, and protect. According to Thomas (2010), animals have become a symbol of man, in opposition to the tradition of domesticating these animals, and consequently, they are seen, almost, as equals.

According to the Associação Brasileira da Industria de Produtos para Animais de Estimação (ABINPET, 2018), now, the act of having a domestic animal has become more popular in Brazil. Instituto Pet Brasil (IPB, 2021), says that this growth is due to at least 70% of the population having or knowing someone who has a pet.

Figure 1- Graph of the growth of the Brazilian pet market
Source: Instituto Pet Brasil (IPB), 2021

Pessanha and Portilho (2008) note that the growth of animal guardianship is due to urbanization and the growth of large cities. Consequently, due to urbanization, the use of the internet to find out about the care of domestic animals was noted, in addition to the development of applications and websites for tours and accommodation for animals.

For Lewgoy, Sordi, and Pinto (2015), the internet a crucial role in improving and advancing animal care, such as veterinary clinics, websites, and networks on the internet.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

This chapter will present the explanation of the theme chosen and the technologies used for the website's development..

2.1. WEBSITES FOR HOSTING DOMESTIC ANIMALS

The domestic animal, in today's society, is seen by many as a member of the family, someone who is part of leisure and travel moments. Unfortunately, many travel locations do not accept pets in their locations, thus leaving pet owners concerned about their well-being. Fortunately, as a result of the advancement of technology, we have migrated to the digital world where there are communities, websites, and applications aimed at the care of animals. For Lewgoy, Sordi, and Pinto (2015), the internet, like veterinary clinics and pet shops, plays an important role in animal care, making the search for information even easier.

2.2. TECHNOLOGIES USED

This topic will explain the technologies used for the development of this project.

2.2.1. HTML

HyperText Markup Language (HTML) is a text markup language used to create web pages that can be accessed on different devices and transmitted over the internet. This language allows users to create and structure sections, paragraphs, headings, and links to other web pages or applications. According to Rezende (2021), HTML allows the organization and formatting of information, enabling the creation of a visually attractive structure for a page.

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
  <title>Formulário</title>
</head>
<body>
  <h1>Formulário</h1>
  <form>
    <label for="nome">Nome:</label>
    <input type="text" id="nome" name="nome">
    <br>
    <br>
    <label for="email">Email:</label>
    <input type="email" id="email" name="email" >
    <br>
    <br>
    <input type="submit" value="Enviar">
  </form>
</body>
</html>
```

Figure 2 - HTML Code Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

In the example above, an HTML code is and the code provided creates the basic structure of a web page. It sets a "form" title for the page and displays it as the main content of the page, and you can enter your name and email address.

According to Mazza (2014), the HTML we write comes to life in browsers when we access our pages and websites, it is essential to have a good understanding of how they work and the challenges that may arise in the process.

However, with the code provided, you already have a minimum structure to start creating a web page. You can add more elements, styles, and functionality as needed to meet your needs. HTML offers the flexibility to create both static and dynamic web pages and allows integration with other technologies.

A screenshot of a web form titled "Formulário" in a large, bold, black serif font. Below the title, there are two input fields. The first is labeled "Nome:" and the second is labeled "Email:". Both labels are in a black serif font. Below the input fields is a button with the text "Enviar" in a black serif font. The entire form is enclosed in a thin black border.

Figure 3 - HTML Page Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

When an HTML file is opened in a browser, a process of interpreting the HTML code takes place to render the page according to the instructions provided. This interpretation involves analyzing the HTML code and transforming the elements present in it into visual elements on the browser screen. According to Silva (2008), When we open a website and we are shown the website we can see it on the computer screen because the page was rendered for us.

The browser goes through the HTML code line by line, analyzing the tags and attributes present. HTML tags provide the basic structure of the document, while attributes provide additional information about how elements should display or behave.

2.2.2.CSS

Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), is a way to style code created in languages such as HTML. Through this practice, it is possible to create a customization layer that improves the appearance of the created code. For Scheidt (2015), CSS is made to style the web page, using style sheets, following the rules and descriptions for rendering the page. Stylesheets are not that difficult to learn and have gained popularity mainly because they are easy to use and allow you to get started quickly. With CSS, you can create visually appealing and sophisticated designs with relatively little effort. According to Zemel (2015), CSS allows us to achieve results that were previously considered impossible or required the use of a large amount of code.

CSS selectors are used to target and style HTML elements on a web page. According to Eis (2012), a selector represents a structure used as a condition to determine which elements of a group of elements will be formatted.

```
h1 {  
  color: #d66000;  
  font-size: 24px;  
  font-family: Arial, sans-serif;  
  text-align: center;  
  margin-top: 20px;  
}
```

Figure 4 - CSS Selector Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

The code presented above is a way of styling an HTML element, which is used to create a main title. These properties allow you to customize the appearance of the title and make it more attractive and readable on the web page.

According to Zemel (2015), when working with CSS, many developers do not pay attention to the way they write CSS selectors. This affects code performance. Therefore, it is crucial to optimize CSS selectors for best performance. Optimizing CSS selectors is essential for good performance and code quality when developing a website.

Figure 5 - CSS Page Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

In the example above, we have an HTML page that uses CSS to style elements. It is important to note that the example given is just a simplified representation of how HTML and CSS work together to create web pages. In a real scenario, it is common to use a variety of HTML elements and more complex CSS styles to make the page interactive.

2.2.3. JAVASCRIPT

JavaScript is a programming language widely used to add interactivity and functionality to web pages. According to Flanagan (2012), JavaScript allows us to script the HTML content and CSS presentation of documents in Web browsers. By creating elements that update automatically, enabling complex interactions and animations, as well as offering features for developing dynamic web applications, JavaScript improves the user experience. According to Silva (2010), the JavaScript, is an language developed for the clients, the functioning of the language depends on information stored in the user's browser.

```
function saudacao() {  
  alert('Olá, amigos!');  
}
```

Figure 6 - JavaScript Code Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

This JavaScript code defines a function called "greeting" that displays a greeting message through a pop-up alert in the browser. The function is defined using the keyword "function", followed by the function name "greeting" and a pair of empty parentheses, indicating that the function takes no arguments.

Figure 7 - JavaScript Page Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

So when this "greeting" function is called somewhere in the code, it will display the message "Hello, friends!" in an alert to the user.

2.2.4. BOOTSTRAP

Bootstrap is an open-source framework widely used for developing rich, responsive user interfaces for websites and web applications. It provides predefined styles, components, and scripts that make it easy to create consistent and professional layouts. Bootstrap is based on HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, allowing developers to quickly create responsive interfaces without having to write all the code from scratch.

According to Souza (2018), this framework offers specific classes to create navigation menus, in addition to ready-made components that facilitate this task, Bootstrap is mainly CSS. Therefore, to use the ready-made components, simply know the names of the classes provided by Bootstrap and apply them in code.

Figure 8 - Bootstrap Link Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

Bootstrap links to CSS and JavaScript are used to add the Bootstrap framework to a website or web application. The link to the CSS file applies Bootstrap styles, while the link to the JavaScript file adds interactivity and Bootstrap-specific functionality.

Figure 9 - Bootstrap Code Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

The example given, is Bootstrap code for a table, which uses the classes and styles provided by Bootstrap to create a table with a nice and responsive appearance.

Figure 10 - Bootstrap Page Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

In short, Bootstrap speeds up the development process by offering consistent styles and reusable components to create responsive, attractive interfaces that make it easier to align elements and create flexible layouts.

2.2.5.MYSQL

MySQL is a relational database management system (RDBMS). Therefore, it represents a set of information organized in tables, organized by columns and rows, facilitating the understanding of the relationships between these tables, which store data. According to Gonçalves (2014), a relational database is a collection of data organized in interconnected tables. MySQL offers a secure and efficient environment to store, organize, and manage large volumes of data in a structured way.

With its relational structure, speed and performance, advanced security, scalability and cross-platform support, MySQL is chosen for its reliability, flexibility, and being free. According to Bento (2021), the MySQL is used in websites because it can be used on different platforms and different languages. It allows the creation of databases that can store different types of information, such as text, numbers and images, using the SQL language to query and manipulate data.

```
1 CREATE DATABASE Users;  
2 USE Users;  
3  
4 CREATE TABLE usuarios (  
5     id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
6     email VARCHAR(255),  
7     senha VARCHAR(255)  
8 );  
9
```

Figure 11 - Creating a Database Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

Due to its reliability, performance, and flexibility, MySQL is widely used in a variety of applications, from small personal websites to large enterprise systems.

#	Nome	Tipo	Agrupamento (Collation)	Atributos	Nulo	Predefinido	Comentários	Extra	Ação
☐	1	id	int(11)		Não	Nenhum			Muda Eliminar Mais
☐	2	email	varchar(255) utf8mb4_general_ci		Sim	NULL			Muda Eliminar Mais
☐	3	senha	varchar(255) utf8mb4_general_ci		Sim	NULL			Muda Eliminar Mais

Figure 12 – Table Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

2.2.6.PHP

Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP) is an open-source server scripting programming language widely used for developing dynamic web applications. According to Bento (2021), PHP is a tool that enables the pre-processing of HTML pages. This way, PHP can change the content of a page before sending it to the browser

```
<?php
$servername = "localhost";
$username = "usuario";
$password = "senha";
$dbname = "banco";

if ($_SERVER["REQUEST_METHOD"] == "POST") {
    $email = $_POST['email'];
    $senha = $_POST['senha'];
    $clicado = isset($_POST['clicado']) ? 1 : 0;

    $conn = new mysqli($servername, $username, $password, $dbname);

    if ($conn->connect_error) {
        die("Falha na conexão: " . $conn->connect_error);
    }

    $sql = "INSERT INTO usuarios (email, senha, clicado) VALUES ('$email', '$senha', $clicado)";

    if ($conn->query($sql) === TRUE) {
        echo "Dados inseridos com sucesso!";
    } else {
        echo "Erro ao inserir dados: " . $conn->error;
    }

    $conn->close();
}
```

Figure 13 - PHP Code Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

The code receives data from the HTML form, the code extracts the information provided, connects to the database, inserts the form data into the corresponding table, and displays a success or error message. After processing, the database connection is closed.

Ola Amigos!!!
Clique aqui para uma saudação!

Endereço de email

Nunca vamos compartilhar seu email com ninguém

Senha

Clique em mim

Figure 14 - Data in the Table Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

The collection of information provided must be stored when entering data, such as email and password.

			id	email	senha
☐	Editar	Copiar	Apagar	1	Hostinho@gmail.com 123
☐	Editar	Copiar	Apagar	2	Little_host@gmail.com 456

Figure 15 - Data in the Table Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

The information provided will be inserted into the specific table in the database. After entering the data, we can do several things with it, such as searching, updating, or deleting it. It's like using a file to find information or correct something that was written wrong.

2.2.7.UML

For UML modeling, there are several types of diagrams created to explain, to both the client and the developer, the system's functionalities. According to Guedes (2009), the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is the visual language that aims to model software based on object-oriented programming.

Goés (2014), says that the UML follows construction steps to prepare the development path that a given software will take, determines the costs, and allows the client to make changes to the project. Below will explain the project's use case diagram, a diagram that explains the main functions of the system and the users who will use the website.

2.2.7.1. USE CASE DIAGRAM

The use case diagram presents the main functions of the project in a way that is easier to understand, both for the client and for software developers, in addition to facilitating the explanation of parts of the project, which the client may often not understand. For Goés (2014), the use case diagram aims to present which modules make up the system and what role each user will play in a given activity that the system will perform.

The use case diagram contains as part of its structure: actors, use cases and associations. According to Guedes (2009), actors represent the roles that users will play in activity with the software, use cases are the system's functionalities and associations are relationships between use cases. The following figure presents an example of a use-case diagram of a bank control system. Containing their respective actors, use cases and associations, designed to represent a banking control system, containing the system's functionalities.

Figure 16 - Use Case Diagram Example
Source: Guedes, 2009

2.2.8. WIREFRAME

Wireframes are used to model the interface part of the project, like UML diagrams, they present to the client and developers an important part, in this case, the design of the project, such as colors, the home page, and other pages that the project needs to have, for its functionality. According to Caitano (2022), the wireframe aims to illustrate the interface of a website or application, helping software developers determine the logical flow between the screens. Wireframes have high and low-fidelity structures.

Figure 17 - Low Fidelity Wireframe Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

Above is a low-fidelity wireframe showing an example of a book to be sold on a bookstore website. Shown below is a high-fidelity wireframe, also featuring a book to be sold.

Figure 18 - High Fidelity Wireframe Example
Source: From the author himself, 2023

According to Graciolli (2020), the low-fidelity wireframe can be executed in a matter of minutes and does not cost much, while the high-fidelity wireframe requires time and costs a lot of money.

3. DEVELOPMENT

In this chapter, the use case diagram will be presented, explaining its general objective and showing the system's functionalities. The high-fidelity wireframe of the home page of the website that was developed will also be presented.

3.1. USE CASE DIAGRAM

In this chapter, the use case diagram of the software that will be developed will be presented, as explained in previous chapters, containing its respective actors, use cases, and associations.

Figure 19 - Use Case Diagram Little Host
Source: From the author himself, 2023

Figure 20 - High Fidelity Wireframe: Home
Source: From the author himself, 2023

In the figure above, the system's use case diagram is presented, containing the actors: host (person who will host the animal), who can register and view accommodation, the tutor (owner of the animal), who can perform registration, view the host, view animal, maintain animal and schedule accommodation and the website administrator, who can maintain the host and maintain the tutor, all users need to log in to perform all other functions, except register.

The figure above shows the home page, which contains information about the website's proposal the role of the host, and how their care can positively impact the animals' lives and the trust of their owners.

Figure 21 - Registration Page for Tutor
Source: From the author himself, 2023

The figure above shows the registration page of the website, where the “Name”, “E-mail” and “Senha” fields are only for the tutor user to register, the user who wants to register as a host must click on the option below the “Cadastrar” button, clicking on the option “Deseja se Cadastrar como Anfitrião? Clique Aqui” the user will be directed to a form page containing the necessary fields to validate as a host, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 22 - Registration Page for Hoster
Source: From the author himself, 2023

4. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The website who will be developed will show a tool for hosting domestic animals, focusing on the care of domestic animals and showing eligible hosts.

The life of domestic animals has a big impact on the life of your tutors, for many times, the animals are a part of the family and when are talk about the care with animals it is a big concern, for be afraid of leaving them in the cares of people who will mistreat these animals. For tutors, this concern may be increased because they don't know whether the host there is qualified for the services. Because of this, this project has the objective of not only hosting animals via the website, but also presenting qualified

professionals to carry out this service, always focusing on the animal's well-being and, for its owners, providing security.

As final considerations, we have that, the development of a website for hosting domestic animals is an important tool as it helps tutors in unexpected moments and presents hosts with job opportunities.

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